

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397

p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 4

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

APRIL 2026
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

Echoes of Expression
A Creative Folio

Volume II, Issue IV (April 2026), National Circulation
ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741
Published Online at www.lakbay-diwapublishing.com
Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

JELISA M. COÑADO

BEEEd Student

Palompon Institute of Technology-Tabango Campus
Sitio Otabon, Poblacion Tabango Leyte, Region VIII, Philippines
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.19688731

A Transformative Field Study Journey

Field Study is an important part of teacher education that allows Field Study students to experience the real classroom setting and connect theory to practice. I was deployed to Tabango North Central School with all my fellow 3rd-year Bachelor of Elementary Education students. My Field Study journey was a life-changing experience that changed how I think about teaching. It provided me with opportunities to observe, assist, and actively participate in different classroom activities. It helped me realize that teaching is not just about delivering lessons or knowledge, but also about guiding, inspiring, and nurturing learners.

On my first day, I focused on observing my cooperating teacher and the learners' behavior. I carefully observed how the teacher managed the class, delivered lessons, and interacted with the learners because I knew the pupils' behavior was different from that of high school students. I observed that Ma'am Maria Lourdes O. Abadines, a grade 4 Science teacher, was patient, kind, and adept at classroom management. The learners were taught to raise their hands before speaking, to ask permission when they leave, and to keep the classroom in order and show respect. I noticed how effective classroom management, clear instructions, and engaging teaching strategies contributed to a productive learning environment.

As the weeks went by, my cooperating teacher gave me responsibilities such as checking students' work, distributing learning materials, and assisting learners who needed help. Especially every morning and before going home, the teacher told them to sweep the floor inside and outside the classroom. These experiences allowed me to interact closely with the students and understand their different learning styles and needs. I realized that each learner is unique and requires patience, understanding, and appropriate strategies to support their learning.

One of the most meaningful experiences I had was assisting my cooperating teacher in the Aral Program, which met every afternoon to improve the reading and comprehension skills of struggling learners. This experience taught me how important it is to be patient, encouraging, and clear when teaching. I learned that slow learners need extra support and guidance, and it is the teacher's responsibility to ensure that no learner is left behind.

There were times when my cooperating teacher was not around. During those moments, I took responsibility for managing the students, maintaining order and ensuring

they stayed focused on their tasks and activities. This allowed me to practice my classroom management skills and build confidence in handling a real classroom setting. I felt overwhelmed and grateful for the experiences because, even though I am only a field study student, the learners treated me as a real teacher. They listened attentively to my instructions and showed me respect at all times. This made me feel valued and strengthened my confidence in handling the class.

Throughout my Field Study, I was exposed to different teaching styles from various teachers, which made me realize that there is no single approach to teaching. Each teacher has their own effective strategies in handling learners and delivering lessons. I also witnessed how my resource teachers showed care for their students, not only in academics but also in their personal well-being. There were times when a student had no food to eat, and the teacher gave money to buy food in the canteen. Building positive relationships with learners helped create a supportive and engaging classroom environment. I also helped with school activities, such as decorating the stage for events and assisting during examinations, which enhanced my cooperation and sense of responsibility.

My Field Study journey was transformative. When I was in my first year, I felt bored with the Bachelor of Elementary Education course and questioned my interest in the program. Everything changed when I was exposed to real classroom settings. I began to enjoy the experience, especially the interaction with the pupils, and I realized that I had developed a genuine interest in teaching children. It helped me grow academically, emotionally, and professionally as a future educator. I learned that teaching is not just a profession but a commitment to shaping learners' minds and lives.